

MEANING GROUPS OF ADJECTIVES IN PERSIAN AND UZBEK LANGUAGE

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Abstract. In this article, theoretical conclusions on the division of adjectives into lexical meaning groups in Persian and Uzbek languages are compared, and the differences between them are highlighted.

Keywords: Phrases, lexical meaning, adjective, past participle, relative adjectives, exclamatory adjective, abstract, indefinite adjective, interrogative adjective, count adjective, ordinal adjective, fractional adjective, reduplicative quantity, numbers or (distributive numbers), display qualities.

According to the lexical and grammatical meaning similarity of the words, some lexical grammatical relationships are entered. Dividing words into groups is considered to be one of the main features along with their grammatical meaning, as well as their lexical meaning. There are word groups that have both grammatical and lexical meaning. Words that take part in a sentence as an independent syntactic part are called independent words. Independent words include: noun, adjective, number, pronoun [3].

In the morphology of the Uzbek language, quality, along with other word groups, occupies a large place. The quality is separated as an independent word group according to its lexical-grammatical characteristics in the Uzbek language [2].

A gradable word that indicates the sign of an object, a partial action, is called an adjective: qora qalam, oq ko'ylak, yaxshi gapirmoq. Another set of words also represents a symbol. But quality differs from them in that it represents a stable and stable sign. For example, Gul – qizil is a static sign, gul qizardi and the variable (dynamic) sign is shown. A quality sign differs from another class sign by its characteristics. For example, qizg'ish – qizil – qip-qizil. Other word groups do not have this feature. On this basis, the adjective can be restored in the form of "mainly indicating the object, partly the action, and appearing in the sentence mainly as a qualifying determiner, sometimes as a participle, and in some cases as a case". The concept of a sign includes color, size, shape, character, weight, taste, etc. According to the nature of the sign, adjectives are divided into two: original adjectives and relative adjectives. In textbooks and manuals, quality is divided into 9 vocabulary groups:

1. Characteristic quality.
2. Status adjective.
3. Formative adjective.
4. Color-denoting quality.
5. Taste quality.
6. Order quality.
7. Quantitative adjective.
8. Positional adjective.

صفت شمارشی (counting adjectives) – Number is studied in the vocabulary.

صفت ترتیبی (adjectives of order) - Number is studied in word order.

صفت کسری (adjectives of fractions) - Number is studied in the vocabulary.

صفت توزیعی (distribution of numbers) - Number is studied in the vocabulary.

صفت اشاره ای (demonstrative adjectives) – Number is studied in word group.

Conclusion

In Uzbek linguistics, adjectives today have 9 lexical meaning groups: Adjectives denoting characteristics; Status adjective; Formative adjective; A quality that expresses color; Taste quality; Odorous quality; Quantitative quality; Positional adjective; Adverb of time.

In Persian, it is divided into 10 groups in terms of lexical meaning: صفت مفعولی (past participle), (relative adjectives) صفت نسبی, صفت تعجبی (exclamation quality), صفت مبهم (abstract, vague quality), صفت پرسشی (interrogative quality), صفت شمارشی (count adjectives), صفت ترتیبی (order adjectives), صفت کسری (fractional adjectives), صفت توزیعی (reduplicative quantity numbers or (distributive numbers), صفت اشاره ای (display qualities).

The results of the observations showed that the lexical meanings of adjectives in Persian are divided into 10 groups, while the adjectives in Uzbek are divided into 9 groups in terms of lexical meaning. In the classification of Persian adjectives into lexical meaning groups, it became clear that the Uzbek adjective is not similar to the lexical meaning group.

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